

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants of Complexes of Ortho-Hydroxy Acetophenones with Manganese and Magnesium

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Metal-ligand stability constants of complexes of substituted ortho-hydroxy acetophenones with bivalent magnesium and manganese were determined potentiometrically, at 30° and at an ionic strength of $\mu \sim 0.1 M$ NaClO₄, in non-aqueous media, 75% dioxane—25% water (v/v). The nature and effect of substituents on the stability of the complexes is discussed.

Proton-ligand stability constants of ortho-hydroxy acetophenones were studied¹ with the view of finding the effect of substituents in the nucleus on the stability of the parent compound. The work was further extended and the metal-ligand stability constants of these ligands were determined^{2,3}. In our present work we are reporting the metal-ligand stability constants of complexes of ortho-hydroxy acetophenones with manganese and magnesium.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique⁴ was utilised in carrying out the three sets of experiments for each complex under study. The precipitation, metal ion hydrolysis and other faults arising during the titrations were taken care of with suitable modifications. The titration vessel and the reagent solutions were thermostated at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. A constant ionic strength of $\mu \sim 0.1 M$ NaClO₄ was maintained. The pH measurements were recorded on 'Elico' pH Meter, Model LI-10 in combination with a saturated Calomel-Glass Electrode assembly. As the ligands were sparingly soluble in water, a non-aqueous medium of 75% dioxane—25% water (v/v) was used throughout the experimental setup. The pH in non-aqueous medium was denoted as B.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The titration curves were treated in usual manner⁵⁻⁷ to get the metal-ligand stability constants. The values of proton-ligand ($\log^p K^H$) and metal-ligand ($\log K$) stability constants thus obtained are reported in Table 1.

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1. P. V. Kamat and M. G. Datar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 409
2. P. V. Kamat and M. G. Datar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (in press).
3. P. V. Kamat and M. G. Datar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (in press).
4. Jennick Bjerrum. *Metal Amino Formation in Aqueous Solution*, P. Hass and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
5. K. E. Jabalpurwalla, K. A. Venkatachalam and M. B. Kabadi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1027.
6. M. Calvin and K. W. Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
7. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.

TABLE 1

Metal-ligand stability constants of Manganese and Magnesium

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°	$\mu \sim 0.1 M NaClO_4$	Metal : ligand = 1 : 4			
Ligand	$\log^p K^H$	Metal	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	
1. 2-Hydroxy acetophenone	11.85	Mn	7.42	—	
		Mg	7.22	—	
2. 2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-acetophenone	11.00	Mn	8.30	—	
		Mg	7.87	—	
3. 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone	10.66	Mn	6.90	5.63	
		Mg	5.31	—	
4. 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone	10.50	Mn	6.82	5.22	
		Mg	6.09	4.15	
5. 2,6-Dihydroxy-4-methyl acetophenone	8.88	Mn	3.25	—	
		Mg	3.56	—	
6. 2-Hydroxy-4-benzyloxy acetophenone	10.33	Mn	5.26	3.73	
		Mg	3.03	—	
7. 2-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy acetophenone	11.35	Mn	6.77	4.37	
		Mg	8.44	—	
8. 2-Hydroxy propiophenone	11.38	Mn	7.42	—	
		Mg	5.52	—	
9. 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-propiophenone	11.30	Mn	7.34	—	
		Mg	5.51	—	

It would be interesting to note that the values of $\log K$ obtained in the present work are comparable with those obtained for structurally similar ligands. Such a data is reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Metal-ligand stability constants of complexes of structurally similar complexes of Mn and Mg

Ligand	$\log^p K^H$	Magnesium		Manganese	
		$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Catechol ⁸	14.20	5.21	3.32	—	—
Salicylaldehyde ⁹⁻¹¹	12.20	3.88	4.30	—	—
		6.25	4.30	3.73	3.06
Salicylic acid ^{9,12}	15.50	4.70	—	5.90	3.90
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy benzoylacetone ¹³	12.28	7.18	6.05	7.66	6.61

The data in Table 2 is mostly chosen for the structurally similar ligands studied under similar experimental conditions such as temperature, composition of the solvent media, the ionic strength, etc. It is rather evident from these constants that the variation of the position and the nature of the substituents in the nucleus has a marked effect on the metal-ligand stability of the complexes. With the exception of *o*-hydroxy benzoylacetone complex with

8. K. S. Math and M. B. Kabadi, Proc. Symposium on the Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds, Agra, (1959), Part III, pp. 65-73.
9. L. G. Van Uitert and W. C. Fernelius, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 375.
10. L. E. Maley and D. P. Mellor, *Nature*, 1947, **159**, 370.
11. L. E. Maley and D. P. Mellor, *Austr. J. Sci. Res.*, 1949, **2A**, 92.
12. D. D. Perrin, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 741.
13. E. H. Holst, Doctor Diss. Pennsylvania State Univ., 1955.

manganese, the values of other complexes of structurally similar ligands are lower than *o*-hydroxy acetophenone complexes. The observed difference may be attributed to the difference in the electronegativity of the substituents. This could also be explained on the basis of the stability of the chelate ring by means of resonance and strength due to the conjugate double bonds, especially for the catechol complexes. In general, metal-ligand complexes of Mn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are weak.

Fig. 1

Plots of $\log K$ against $\log P_K^H$ indicate that the magnitude of the slopes of the linear straightlines is greater than unity, i.e., 1.32 for manganese and 1.27 for magnesium (Figure 1). This finding definitely indicates that the nuclear substitution has brought about a change in the stability of the metal complexes to a greater extent than the corresponding proton complexes¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

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14. L. G. Van Uitert, W. C. Fernelius and B. E. Douglas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 457, 2736, 3862.
15. D. D. Perrin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3125.
16. S. P. Datta and B. R. Rabin, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **52**, 1117.
17. S. P. Datta, R. Leberman and B. R. Rabin, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 1982, 2141.